

OPEN SCHOOL MODEL TO IMPROVE INTERPERSONAL SKILLS OF MARGINALIZED CHILDREN

NGURAH AYU NYOMAN MURNIATI^{1*}, ENDANG WURYANDINI², NOOR MIYONO³ and ALFIAH⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Universitas PGRI Semarang, Indonesia.

*Corresponding Author Email: ngurahayunyoman@upgris.ac.id,

Email: ²wuryandiniendang5@gmail.com, ³noormiyono@upgris.ac.id, teachingclinic2013@gmail.com

Abstract

Children have the same rights to get protection and assistance. Children need complete services to develop and be independent and creative, including children from marginal groups. In this effort, an open-school model was designed to improve interpersonal skills. The research was carried out using a Research and Development (R&D) design. Phase 1 is carried out to explore the essential characteristics and abilities of children from marginal groups. The model design is based on the findings of the empirical data. The design of model design is validated to obtain accuracy, accuracy, and implementation in improving Interpersonal Skills. Phase 2 was carried out to test the effectiveness of the model. The results showed that the Open School model was developed from the Teaching Clinic in an outdoor classroom with two classes: the fundamental ability class and the independent ability class. The expert validation results showed that the average model's feasibility (consistency and accuracy) was 90.22%. The FGD results showed that the implementation of the model was 87.17%. The results of the limited test show that the model is effective in increasing the self-development (Interpersonal Skills) of marginal children $t\text{-count} (12,593) > \text{critical } t (1,746)$ and $t \text{ count } (7,804) > \text{critical } t (1,688)$ in the extended test. This shows that dynamic treatment must be designed because of the dynamic characteristics of marginal children. The model's generalization must consider the characteristics and potential of marginalized children in the local area. Recommendations are given to related parties to increase independence and prevent back on the road.

Keywords: Model, Open School, Interpersonal Skills

INTRODUCTION

Semarang, one of the big cities on the island of Java, has become a place of consideration for migration and/or urbanization. This can be seen from BPS data (2021) in the Table of Population Development Indicators in 2020. According to the data, the population density of the city of Semarang has increased, although population growth and inward migration have decreased. This fact shows an unrecorded increase in the "stealth population" that affects population density. The impact of population density and the Covid-19 pandemic is the phenomenon of poverty. Poverty results in reduced or even lost fulfillment of children's fundamental rights. This will result in, among other things, child neglect. The fulfillment of children's rights is relatively low and hinders them from getting a decent education and life.

Marginal groups are marginalized groups for various social reasons. One part of the marginalized group is street children. Street children are marginalized and far from eligible to live and be educated. Suyanto (2010) defines street children as children who are excluded, marginalized, and eliminated from loving treatment and face a harsh and unfriendly city environment. Street children are categorized as neglected children. Abandoned children are

cared for by the state. Law Number 23 of 2002 concerning Child Protection explains that abandoned children are children whose needs are not appropriately met. Inappropriate treatment received by children can be seen physically, psychologically, spiritually, emotionally, and socially.

The daily reality of street children is vulnerable to social problems, such as crime and sexual and social exploitation. The mindset of street children and the marginalized, according to Nitayadnya (2016), prioritizes activities that are considered capable of generating money so that the welfare of their lives and the burden on their families is reduced. Changes in mindset occur as life experiences are experienced.

Understanding the marginalized group of street children must be related to their self-concept. According to Burns (1993), the self-concept professionally has comprehensive parts of human behavior. Muslim and Murdiyati (2004) explain that the self-concept of street children significantly influences the overall behavior shown. Street children tend to withdraw from contact with other people or be aggressive. The interaction and communication that are built are not very good. Their interpersonal skills are relatively low. Self-existence is a person's action potential in choosing and making decisions about himself and his environment. Self-existence is strongly influenced by interactions with others, society, the environment, and the system.

One form of interaction skills is interpersonal skills. Interpersonal skills are a person's basic skills in dealing with other people (interacting). Buhrmester (1996) states that interpersonal competence is essential to building, fostering, and maintaining close interpersonal relationships with parents, friends, and partners. Paramarsi (2016) states that communication aspects, including source-receivers, influence interpersonal skills, messages conveyed feedback, feedforward, communication channels, communication barriers, communication ethics, and communication competence. Johnson (2002) explains that the process of interpersonal skills consists of 4 (four) things, namely 1) getting to know and trusting someone through openness, 2) communicating with each other appropriately and clearly, 3) accepting and supporting each other, and responding and paying attention to people's problems. Others, and communicate acceptance and support appropriately, 4) resolve conflicts in constructively dealing with others.

The initial findings are shown in Table 1. The results of interviews conducted with 10 marginal children in the Telogosari, Kali and Poncol areas.

Table 1: Initial Description of Marginal Group Children's Interpersonal Skills

No	Indicator	f	Percentage
1	Response/attention	5	50%
2	Courage to express opinions	2	20%
3	Ability to interact	3	30%

Table 1 shows the low communication skills of street children. Complicated interactions and easy prejudice can be seen in the findings of the initial observations. Therefore, there is a need for an in-depth study of the interpersonal skills of marginalized groups of children, especially

on 1) the skills to respond and pay attention to the focus of conversation/communication, 2) the courage to express opinions, and 3) the ability to interact. The dimensions of interpersonal skills above are essential in interacting and preparing to enter real social life.

Sarwono (2003) explains that entering a broad social life is part of the developmental task that must be undertaken. This means that every child (in all its forms of backgrounds) will undergo the developmental task of having a life and social environment. So it is necessary to prepare basic skills related to social life. All the challenges of life will develop according to the times. The need for self-ability and independence is a measure of survival and development. Through education, we will be able to change the perspective of society towards fulfilling basic skills as a provision for the younger generation to work and be meaningful in the future. Education is not only interpreted as formal education. Education must be able to change the perspective of society and be able to give birth to a superior generation that is responsive to the surrounding environment. This follows the opinion of Tilaar (2012) that education and social change are closely related. Social change society cannot be separated from the community's level of education.

Educational needs or learning needs are addressed by all people regardless of which economic group the person comes from, both young and old (Fadjar, 2005). Therefore, understanding the need for education is essential in preparing street children to become a demanding generation ready to fight for the future. Through education, intellectuals will be enlightened to achieve a meaningful life. This meaningful life will bring every child find meaning in life (Abdurrahman, 2007).

The Open School concept was developed from the form of a natural school with more systematic management and had clear and measurable learning outcomes. Rohimah (2014) states that the natural school is one of the educational paradigms that can explore dialogical abilities that are humble, compassionate, and open to criticism. Learning emphasizes awareness of learning needs and harmonious communication between parties. Schools provide the ability to be creative, explore, and discover students' potential. The school facilitates the exploration of knowledge based on reality.

The Open School concept was developed in the study of the Kolong Langit School by Retnaningdyastuti, Murniati, and Handayani (2017). A school was developed to equip students with clinical skills in the Teaching Clinic. The school under the sky was developed as a form of semi-formal school and supported their formal school with an academic atmosphere built to support children learning in the open. The school under the sky positively impacts increasing the willingness to learn of children from marginal groups. The problem faced is the variety and number of students who change every time. This requires further analysis. The utilization of the Teaching Clinic as a learning clinic has not been implemented optimally.

A teaching Clinic is a model or forum for improving and developing human resource capabilities, especially human educational resources (Murniati, 2013). Murniati (2013) states that clinical activities in the Teaching Clinic are carried out through stages 1) setting clinical goals and objectives; 2) identifying the problems of the participants and grouping them into

mentoring groups according to the main tasks and functions; 3) group assistance according to the problem, or with other notes; 4) evaluation and reflection on clinical achievements. This basis is the basis for building an open school. By looking at the characteristics of children from marginal groups, it is hoped that open schools will be one solution to improve their basic abilities and independence.

The learning system at the Open School is very flexible and different from homeschooling and/or other forms. Study time is not as systematic as in traditional schools. The amount of study time is set tiered. For the low class, the whole study day is 2 hours, and for the middle class is 4 hours. Furthermore, the high class is 6 hours. At the same time, the time system applied is a system of fines. This means that if within 1 day of learning is scheduled during meeting hours at the class level, and students cannot follow it, it must be replaced the next time, and so on, except for exceptional cases.

The preparation of a formidable golden generation is not only supported by lucky children. Children from marginalized groups also need attention. Therefore, the learning content is directed at meeting the needs and independence of students. The development of students' potential is directed at improving critical thinking, creativity, and communication skills. Dyers et al. (2011) explain that two-thirds of a person's critical, creative, and innovative abilities are obtained through education. In addition, good communication will establish the ability to interact well. Communication will support the achievement of critical, creative, and innovative analysis. Interpersonal skills are a challenge for the 21st-century generation. Interpersonal skills are not only intelligence but are more of an immediate need that must be possessed. The formation of skills that support creativity becomes very important. Learning does not only look at learning outcomes as the final achievement but more on life skills. Modifying activities will affect learners' retention and motivation (Roof and Kreuter 2010).

The change in the educational paradigm due to changes in the global era and the Covid-19 pandemic became the inspiration to develop Kolong Langit School into an open school that can develop the potential of marginalized children to be independent based on ability. The development of open schools through Teaching Clinics is expected to improve children's interpersonal skills from marginal groups. The Open School Model is expected to be able to achieve this goal.

RESEARCH METHODS

The overall research design uses a Research and Development (R&D) approach, as shown in Figure 1. The research results describe the characteristics, potentials, and self-development framework of the marginal groups that are the research subjects. The development results are carried out as a form of model development in revealing its role and effectiveness in improving the interpersonal skills of marginalized children. The research steps using Sugiyono's R&D stages (2018) include research potential and problems, model design formulation, model design validation, improvement, limited testing, model improvement and determination, and extensive testing.

Stage research uses a survey-type quantitative approach. This type of research is used to collect data on the characteristics and potential of marginalized children in the city of Semarang who are the research subjects. This survey research is intended to examine the behavior of individuals/groups. The survey design used is Survey Sample Design. The results of the survey research findings are then described in the self-model of children from marginal groups.

The open school model which was developed from the school under the sky model through the stages of Figure 1.

Figure 1: R&D Step

The limited and extensive test used a sample of 28 people with details of 8 people for the limited test consisting of 5 men and 3 women and 20 people for the extended test (12 men and 8 women). The sampling method is purposive random sampling.

The research sample was selected for children aged 7-16 years who were in the area of 8 observation points (Tugu Muda, Gajahmada, Gayamsari, Bangkong, Johar, Tlogosari, Poncol, and Tawang). An experimental group is a group of quasi-street children with a place to live. The control group is children who work on the street, still have families, and attend school.

Methods of data collection using questionnaires, observation, and documentation. The constructs of the theory and construct test instruments can be seen in Table 2. The questionnaire contains the criteria for a Likert Scale of 1-5. The interpersonal skill observation questionnaire also contains criteria 1) BT (not yet visible) if students have not shown strenuous effort; 2) MT (starts to appear) if students have shown effort even though they are not consistent; 3) MB (starting to develop) if students show serious effort quite often/consistently enough; 4) M (cultured) if students show a severe and consistent effort; 5) MMT (starting to be an example) if students show severe and consistent efforts and can be role models for others.

Table 2: Dimensions of Interpersonal Skills

No.	Dimensions	Indicators
1	Response and Attention	a. Observe the interlocutor in a friendly manner
		b. Listen carefully
		c. Not interrupting the conversation
		d. Empathy
		e. Sensitive to other people's responses
2	Courage to express opinions	a. Have a concept
		b. Write down the concept
		c. Arrange various concepts
		d. Be loud
		e. Able to explain
3	Ability to interact	a. Ability to interact with peers
		b. Ability to interact with educators
		c. Ability to interact with parents/others who are older
		d. Ability to interact with people outside the system

The data analysis method for the limited and extended tests used the Quasi-Experimental Pretest-Posttest Group Design method. Quasi-research steps in measuring the results of both limited and comprehensive tests are 1) identifying and limiting problems only for limited/widespread testing; 2) establishing research hypotheses; 3) determining the research subject; 4) doing a pre-test; 5) giving treatment to the selected experimental group; 6) do posttest; 7) processing and analyzing the results. The alternative hypothesis is that open schools are effective in improving interpersonal skills. Hypothesis testing uses a simple t-test through a comparison of the mean pre-test and post-test. If the value of t counts < from the t table, then the null hypothesis is accepted, and vice versa.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result

Description of Characteristics and Potential of Marginalized Children

The results of mapping and analysis of the characteristics and potential of marginalized children who are the subject of the study can be seen in Table 3. The research subjects at 8 observation points totaled 20 people.

Table 3: Profile of Street Children

No	Indicators	Finding
1	Category:	
	a. Vulnerable streets	40
	b. Street children	10
	c. Working on the road	50
2	Age:	
	a. < 5 years	20
	b. 6-12 years	50
	c. >12 years old	50
3	Time on the road every day:	
	a. > 6 hours	75
	b. < 6 hours	25
4	Family Relations:	
	a. There is a family	80
	b. No family	20
5	Setting on the street:	
	a. Poor / helping parents	90
	b. Run away from home	5
	c. Follow friends	5

Table 3 shows that the group of marginalized children encountered, on average, is a vulnerable group. Most of them come from low-income families who have to be on the road to help their parents. The category of pure street children is challenging in the scope of observation. Because these categories of children do not stay in one place, they move from place to place.

On average, the children were found to have more than 6 hours of walking time each day. This is very concerning. On average, they are on the road from 1-3 years old. At first, they played, followed their parents, and then worked. However, some of them go to school and have high aspirations for the future.

Further description of the results of research on the basic abilities of children in marginal groups can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4: Profile of Basic Ability

No	Indicators	Finding
1	Education	
	a. School	50
	b. Ever School	30
	c. No school	20
2	Basic Abilities	
	a. Read Write	
	1) Good	50
	2) Fair	30
	3) Less	20
	b. Communication	
	1) Good	20
	2) Fair	60
	3) Less	20
	c. Positive Thinking	
	1) Good	0
	2) Enough	40
	3) Less	60
	d. Leader	
	1) Good	20
	2) Fair	30
	3) Less	50
	e. Introvert	
	1) Yes	70
	2) No	30

Table 4 shows the profile of marginalized children who are the research subjects. Some feel that their education is at school, while others do not. The essential abilities possessed are relatively low. The ability to read and write is not too visible. Even though on average, they can read and write, although with less than optimal results. Relatively low communication skills. They tend to be passive when dealing with other people and tend to be introverted and introverted. They are grouped according to the area of the street. Furthermore, with the help of third parties, such as volunteers and others, self-development is carried out. Further description of Table 4 can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Basic Abilities of Marginalized Children

The description of these basic abilities encourages researchers to be able to design schools that can involve them as students. The form of an open school is adapted to their characteristics and potential.

Open schools are a development of child-friendly schools. The difference between an open and child-friendly school lies in the objectives and technical implementation. Open schools are more open in implementing education, although they are systematic but not tiered. The Kolong Langit School is almost like a formal and tiered school. Open schools are more aimed at preparing students for independence. The open school model can be seen in Figure 3. The input of the open school students is children from marginal groups. The Open School is a non-formal school model for street children built in the openness of the universe. Learners will be analyzed through the Teaching Clinic. Murniati and Wuryandini (2021) show that open schools have learning outcomes directed at the formation of interpersonal skills and independence of students based on the limits of reading, writing, and arithmetic, as well as communication and interaction skills. The Open School Model is organized into two groups/classes: the fundamental ability class and the independent ability class.

Figure 3: The Open School Model

The results of the model validation can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Model Validation Results

No	Category	Validator (%)	
		I	II
1	Model	82.5	83
2	Guidelines	80	85
	Validation Mean	81.25	84
1	Model Improvement	87.5	90
2	Guideline Improvement	90	93,375
	Average Repair	88.75	91.6875

The validator's findings indicate the need to improve the readability of the model and supporting guidelines. Improvements in expert validation were carried out to achieve a feasibility rate of 85%.

The recapitulation of the validation and improvement scores can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6: Recapitulation of Average Validation of Experts and Practitioners

No	Category	Validator (%)		Average
		I	II	
1	Average Validation	81.25	84	82.63
2	Average Improvement	88.75	91.69	90.22
3	Practitioner Average			87.17

The open school model shows accuracy, consistency, and implementation, with an average validation of experts and practitioners > 85% as shown in Table 6.

The results of the limited and extended test can be shown in Table 7 and Table 8. Table 7 shows the results of the limited test. If $H_{0:1} \geq 2$ (there is no difference/same/less slightly between pre-test and post-test limited test). $H_{a:1} < 2$ (The result of the pretest is smaller than the result of the post test of the limited test).

Table 7. Limited Test Results

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances (Limited Test)		
	79,33333	50,6667
Mean	77,59259144	58,03704
Variance	7,799378441	13,90124
Observations	9	9
Pooled Variance	10,85030992	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	16	
t Stat	12,59375642	
P(T<=t) one-tail	5,09E-10	
t Critical one-tail	1,745883676	
P(T<=t) two-tail	1,01886E-09	
t Critical two-tail	2,119905299	

The results of the analysis in Table 7 show t count (12.593) > critical t (1.746) or p value (5.09E-10 < 0.05). This means that Ho is rejected or Ha is accepted.

Table 8 shows the results of the extended test. If $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$ (there is no difference/same/less slightly between the pre-test and post-test of the extended test). $H_a: \mu_1 < \mu_2$ (The result of the pretest is smaller than the result of the post test of the extended test).

Table 8 Extensive Test Results

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances		
	52	49,3333
Mean	62,26316	53,31579
Variance	16,14294	8,833019
Observations	19	19
Pooled Variance	12,48798	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	36	
t Stat	7,803886	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1,49E-09	
t Critical one-tail	1,688298	
P(T<=t) two-tail	2,98E-09	
t Critical two-tail	2,028094	

The results of the analysis in Table 8 show t count (7.804) > critical t (1.688) or p value (1.49E-9 < 0.05). This means that Ho is rejected or Ha is accepted.

Tables 7 and 8 show an effective model in improving the skills of marginalized children who are the research subjects. The effectiveness is shown from the increase in the pretest and posttest scores as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Pretest and Posttest Recapitulation

DISCUSSION

Children are born protected and have dignity, self-respect, and honor that must be maintained appropriately (Handayani, 2013). Children must be protected by their abilities and rights to grow, develop, and participate optimally.

The open school is one of the under-the-sky school models that were developed to improve marginalized children's essential abilities and independence. Open schools better prepare marginalized children to manage and improve interpersonal skills for independence and interaction. Interpersonal skills are the ability of each person to interact with other people. A person's ability to manage himself effectively in completing work or completing tasks, or interacting with others (Monczka et al., 2020).

Interpersonal skills are the ability to communicate or interact. These skills include good communication skills, the ability to be a good listener, and a good attitude and empathy for others. Spencer & Spencer (1993) divide interpersonal skills into four parts, namely 1) concern for order, 2) initiatives; 3) impact and influence; skills information seeking. Meanwhile, Robbins and Judge (2014) focus on interpersonal skills in various basic abilities or those that support the basic abilities possessed by everyone in the communication process.

Therefore, the Open School model can be developed to achieve the basic abilities of marginalized children by improving interpersonal skills. Interpersonal skills will be the basis for developing communication and interaction skills. This is in line with the research of Suradi (2003); Setiawan (2007); Aman, Ngadirin Setiawan, and Lia Yuliana (2014).

Schools or whatever form, such as shelters, communities, and so on, will be a place for marginalized children to develop themselves. Data support from research results and several relevant studies show that marginal children who are often called street children who have attended school or are currently in school will have different basic abilities from street children who have never attended school. Suradi's research (2003) shows a tendency to change behavior patterns for the better in a group of children in a halfway house. Although not very significant, changes in behavior such as smoking, drinking, Malak, disputes with friends, and doodles on the wall decreased. The role of the halfway house can reduce the desire of marginalized children to return to the streets. Furthermore, marginalized children's learning desire is increasing. This is a support for them to develop themselves through education.

Research support Setiawan (2007) shows that it is necessary to identify the needs of marginalized children in developing themselves as a form of fulfilling children's rights. Awareness of children's rights raises the role and contribution to achieving child protection goals, including marginalized groups of children. Furthermore, this will be achieved through the implementation of the Community Based. Through the Community Based model, it is hoped that independence, concern, and harmony will be achieved by utilizing internal and external potentials. The role of families and communities to support marginalized children does not return to the streets. The research of Aman, Ngadirin Setiawan, and Lia Yuliana (2014) shows that through character education, children can develop personal and social abilities. This will help develop the essential skills that build children's character and care and help them solve

problems personally. The support of these studies shows the importance of a forum for street children to develop themselves, instill character, and provide understanding not to return to the streets.

Another thing observed by this research is that children are on the road because of adult intervention; children are on the streets because of the influence of their parents. Therefore, their character and potential are relatively low. Children do not understand their potential and have low communication skills. They are only material/money oriented.

This setting becomes the focus of class mapping in basic and independent ability classes. The introductory skills class will cover the basic skills of reading, writing, and arithmetic. Independent skills classes will cover communication/interpersonal skills, basic entrepreneurial skills, or entrepreneurship. The learning achievement in the Calistung class (Reading, Writing, and Counting) is that students can read, write and count according to elementary school primary education achievement. The learning achievement in the independent ability class is the achievement of simple indicators of interpersonal skills and simple entrepreneurship to face life and change in the global era. The support of parents and the community is very high to overcome the problems of these marginal children.

Although the open school model can increase marginal children's interpersonal skills, the increase does not occur significantly. Many limitations occur and must be considered to become an understanding in the process of managing and providing education in open schools. Coordination between teams becomes very important to achieve the expected goals. So improvements are still needed regarding measuring further learning performance from educators and students.

The open school learning system has different learning outcomes and curriculum from formal schools. The character of different students is then tried to overcome with different school treatments. The open school model does not yet refer to standardization of education as does formal school. The implementation of formal education must refer to eight standards (graduate competency, content, process, assessment, educators and education personnel, facilities, infrastructure, management, and education financing standards. Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia number 17 of 2010, article 1 paragraph 2 states that the implementation of education is the implementation of components of the education system in academic units or programs on the path, level, and type of education so that the education process can take place following national education goals.

The implementation of open schools is not yet based on educational standards. However, its implementation is directed based on these standards. Utomo (2015), in his research, describes the system and implementation at the Kaliabang Tengah Open Middle School. The learning system uses input, process, and output systems. The findings show that the conventional system is far from expectations. This is due to many factors, including the condition of students, educators, and infrastructure. Putra, Hasanah, and Nuriyah (2015) research use a Community Based and Street in providing education for street children. This approach combines the program through the empowerment of shelters with education and skills training, and moral

education. The impact seen from this research is that there is a positive impact that causes street children to have knowledge and independence so that they do not move on the road again.

Street children in shelters or the form of community/open schools are educated to have life skills to meet their own needs independently. Problems that arise are often found in the implementation of education. The program that is prepared is not incidental but must be sustainable. Pelonis et al. (2009) explained that continuing education strengthens skills, knowledge, and problem-solving abilities and makes decisions about academic interests and learning development.

Monitoring and evaluation activities are carried out to obtain a match between planning and empowerment processes that are useful in developing teaching and learning abilities (Kitchen and Jeurissen 2006). Continuing education includes all aspects of intelligence development (spiritual, emotional, social, intellectual, and kinesthetic) so that evaluation and monitoring are directed to see learning achievement.

Implementing an open school uses participatory service, sustainability, empowerment, multi-effect, and social control principles. Participation services are developed by emphasizing a sense of community and sharing. Participation is more emphasized in community agreement in seeing social change so that they can participate according to applicable institutions.

The role of parents is significant in supporting open-school education programs. To prevent children from going to and returning to the road, the role of parents is directed at good parenting. The principle of parenting involves the role of parents/family in providing education. The involvement of family roles is mainly related to skill improvement and moral education for troubled or problem-prone families. Family empowerment is carried out in stages using a social and clinical approach. Setiawan (2007) further confirms in his research that knowledge and skills help refer to needs-based related services.

The success of the open school model for groups of marginalized children who are the subject of research cannot be separated from the commitment and integrity of volunteers in assisting open schools. According to the guidelines in the model developed, mentoring is based on identifying the characteristics and potential of marginalized children so that treatment can be mapped according to their needs. Mentoring is carried out to help marginalized children to be able to identify and express their needs and to be able to identify the fundamental problems faced in connection with the basic demands of developing their capacity to overcome various life problems and changes.

Implementing education in open schools can identify the needs of students based on their potential and characteristics. This capacity building is based on clinical studies in the Teaching Clinic to identify children who need basic level assistance and those who need more level of assistance in independence towards entrepreneurial skills. The achievement of basic abilities is obtained by nature-based learning using a limited and straightforward infrastructure. However, their enthusiasm and the support of volunteers and the community strengthen the achievement of educational goals. Communication skills, which are part of interpersonal skills, can be seen from the response and attention, courage to express opinions, and ability to interact. The

improvement is mainly found in learning to listen carefully to what the other person is talking about and not trying to interrupt when he is talking. Although not too large, the increase that occurs is a response to changes in learning outcomes. Another improvement can be seen in the courage and quality of expressing opinions. Compared to responsiveness and attention, the improvement in this dimension was not very large. This is understood as a continuous learning process. When marginalized children continuously learn in their class or community, their knowledge and skills will increase.

Furthermore, this will support the quality of their responses or opinions. The dimension of the ability to interact shows an increase in the indicators of the ability to interact with peers and volunteers who become educators/companions. The quality of the interaction can be well described for these indicators. As for other indicators, some parts have not been seen, and some are slightly visible. This is a note for further improvement.

The improvement of interpersonal skills appears from the limited test to the extended test as shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Figure 5: Description of Limited Results

The test results in Figure 5 show that the dimensions of response and attention have a higher score than the dimensions of courage to express opinions and the ability to interact. While in Figure 6, after following the process for a long time in open schools and the number of students, the dimensions of response and attention were obtained, having a lower score than the dimension of courage to express opinions. While the dimensions of the ability to interact. Stay on the lowest score. What needs to be considered and taken into account is the handling of marginal children. Small-class learning will provide maximum results in increasing responsiveness and attention, and the courage to express opinions. The dimension of the ability to interact will look better if there is a large class.

Figure 6: Description of Extended Results

The research findings above need to be explored in-depth to find a more general model for handling children from marginal groups. This is because handling marginalized children is casuistic and depends on the characteristics of children from marginal groups in the area that is the research subject.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The open school model is built based on the characteristics and profiles of marginalized children in Semarang, which are very varied and dynamic. Generalizing the model requires other in-depth research, especially in achieving the expected behavior.
2. The results of expert validation show an average score of 90.22; this means the model is feasible to use. Practitioner validation through FGD showed an average of 87.17, which means that the model can be implemented.
3. The results of the analysis of the effectiveness of the model in the limited test show t count (12.593) > critical t (1.746), and the results of the extended test analysis show t count (7.804) > critical t (1.688). This means that the model effectively improves marginalized children's interpersonal skills in a limited or extended test.

Suggestion

In this study, the differences in the findings in the limited and broad trials indicate differences in the provision of treatment, services, and assistance by taking into account the following:

1. Characteristics and profiles of local marginalized children.
2. Time to reveal the potential in the profile. A long time will reveal much better results than a short time.
3. Complex understanding of sustainability of model implementation due to limited time, cost, and opportunity in exploring needs and changes based.

4. Cooperation of related parties in overcoming the problems of marginalized children. A positive response will help the implementation of activities with maximum results.

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